

Roadmap for Ethical Use of Generative AI (GenAI) tools

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Roadmap for Ethical Use of LLMs and Gen AI tools

Summary

This roadmap presents a 5-step information guide to using generative AI tools (GenAI), including large language models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT. The aim is to raise awareness of some ethical issues in uses of these nascent AI models that generate text, audio and video. Issues include an AI digital divide: those who do not understand *what AI is*, nor how they can access or use it; those who may not know the difference between machine learning and artificial intelligence; those who use a free version of a GenAI tool as a daily personal assistant, and those who can pay the cost of using advanced models. In using these systems **we as users are**, in the words of Ed Zitron, CEO of a US Media Relations and Public Relations company [EZPR](#), something “**between a lab rat and an unpaid intern, with the goal to juice as much value from the interaction as possible**” (2024: from here: [Never Forgive Them](#)). Continuous co-learning with different stakeholders, including businesses to meet their needs, staying up to date with the variety of tools will be key to appropriate and productive application of AI tools in a changing labour market.

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Step 1: Understanding AI, Generative AI & Agentic AI

While AI companies and influencers promote Generative AI (GenAI) tools such as large language models (LLMs), producing output in the style of some level of human performance ([OpenAI, n.d.](#); [Mollick, 2025](#)), there should be no compulsion to pay for the use of LLMs that summarise text content, or tools that produce audio, images or videos - GenAI.

Generative AI “refers to a class of AI models, that analyses large amounts of data and generates new content, including text, images, and code, that mirrors human expression” ([Microsoft, n.d.](#)). The ‘best’ models with ‘agency’ (AI Agents) claimed to perform at PhD level deep research capability ([Edwards, 2025](#); [Sunil, 2025](#)), can cost \$20,000 per month for single use licences. AI agents are “systems or programs capable of autonomously performing tasks on behalf of a user or another system by designing its workflow and utilizing Accessible tools” (IBM, 2025).

The science of artificial intelligence (AI), rooted in the scholarship of 20th century mathematician and Bletchley Park codebreaker, **Alan Turing**, is concerned with exploring and simulating human thinking in machines ([Shah and Warwick, 2010](#)). Turing considered “the learning of languages would be the most impressive” of human activities (Turing, 1948: p.509 in Cooper & van Leeuwen, 2013). That idea drove the direction of early AI research in the mid-1950s towards natural language processing (NLP), and natural language understanding (NLU). This was alongside engineering a machine to play chess, considered one activity of intelligent humans. The first artificial language system, enabling conversation between human and machine, appeared in the mid-1960s. **Eliza**, a computer programme with 250 lines of code created by computer scientist Joseph Weizenbaum simulated a psychologist in its interaction with humans ([Weizenbaum, 1966](#)). IBM’s **Deep Blue** machine achieved a historic close victory, in a man vs. machine chess game, over the then chess grandmaster Gary Kasparov in 1997 ([IBM, n.d.](#)).

We have become accustomed to losing to chess-playing machines. In a very short time, in less than a decade, we have invited voice-activated AI assistants in our home, such as Amazon’s Alexa. However, modern artificial language models (LMs) “have been increasing in size as measured by the number of parameters and size of training data” and are considered by some as “stochastic parrots” ([Bender, et al., 2021](#)). Current LLMs are disembodied, they do not learn from outdoor play (Bilton, 2025), or experience grazing their knee in the garden or at a local park. Hence concerns about these systems include i) lack of real-world experiential knowledge revealed in nonsensical answers on occasion, b) usage through ‘prompts’ (conversing, putting questions to GenAI), training AI models for free, and especially iii) over the energy consumption of these nascent AI technologies:

“Large language models such as ChatGPT are some of the most energy-guzzling technologies of all. Research suggests, for instance, that about [700,000 litres of water](#) could have been used to cool the machines that trained ChatGPT-3 at Microsoft’s data facilities” (Professor Mariana Mazzucato in the Guardian, May 2024: [The ugly truth behind ChatGPT: AI is guzzling resources at planet-eating rates | Mariana Mazzucato | The Guardian](#)).

Step 2: Data Protection and Privacy Issues in Gen AI & Agentic AI

Current state-of-the-art in Gen AI and LLMs “have no relationship with truth”, nor do they ‘know facts’. These tools might give an impression of understanding, but this is an illusion since they have no visceral experience to draw upon. (Emeritus AI Professor Gary Marcus, 28 November 2024: [ChatGPT, at Age Two - Marcus on AI](#)).

In addition to the now infamous problem of ChatGPT’s inability to count the number of times ‘r’ appears in the word ‘strawberry’, or correctly list the names of US states with ‘r’ in them, disappointments balance the claims of productivity. From [OpenAI’s community forum](#), this is one user’s perspective of OpenAI’s [o1 model](#) not living up to the hyped-up claims on its performance:

[Thomas11]: “After having spent a couple of days implementing support for O1 in our middleware, my conclusion so far is that I’m actually disappointed by it. It might be much smarter and capable of reasoning than gpt-4o, but the API differences, especially the lack of streaming, is simply too painful for us to be able to deal with... for 100% of our use cases, which includes about 50 different clients, it’s simply not interesting at all.”

Alongside some faulty responses, another concern of these AI tools is the amount of information you share with a GenAI system. More so the amount of personal and possibly confidential details you might have to disclose to an Agentic AI in order for it to act as realistic and autonomous assistants.

On data protection, Ruschemeier (2024) summarises the landscape from studies highlighting that “**LLMs are able to memorise training data** ... thus reducing the capacity to generalise to new data ... **Larger models** with more parameters “**remember**” more data than smaller models... **Violations of people’s privacy and right to data protection** result from both incorrect information and correct information they do not want published”.

On **privacy and security**, Meredith Whittaker, who founded Google Open Research, is co-founder of the [AI Now Institute](#), and President of [Signal](#) app, warns that using AI agents is like “putting your brain in a jar,” and that the:

“type of access the AI agent would need ... including access to our web browser and a way to drive it as well as access to our credit card information to pay for tickets, our calendar, and messaging app to send the text to your friends” ([Tech Crunch, 2025](#)).

Whittaker raises awareness of what else an AI Agent would need to perform tasks on our behalf or when assisting us:

“... would need to be able to drive that [process] across our entire system with something that looks like root permission, accessing every single one of those databases — probably in the clear, because there’s no model to do that encrypted. And if we’re talking about a sufficiently powerful ... AI model that’s powering that, there’s no way that’s happening on device. That’s almost certainly being sent to a cloud server where it’s being processed and sent back. So there’s a **profound issue with security and privacy** that is haunting this **hype around**

agents, and that is ultimately threatening to break the blood-brain barrier between the application layer and the OS layer by conjoining all of these separate services [and] muddying their data”.

Using AI tools comes with regulatory responsibility: compliance with the UK’s 2018 Data Protection Act (the general data protection regulation - GDPR) and other legislation (e.g. [Online Safety Act](#)). Caution and attention to fundamental rights should entrench true informed consent, purpose limitation and other GDPR principles to achieve best practice in use of these AI tools.

Step 3: Understanding copyright infringement and risk of job losses.

Generative AI tools “cannibalise human creativity” according to the [CISAC 2024](#) report: **Global economic study shows human creators’ future at risk from generative AI.**

These tools also “memorise and regurgitate copyrighted information they have been trained on” ([Louis Hunt](#), previously CFO and VP BD of MIT spin-off [LiquidAI](#)). The tragic case of OpenAI whistleblower, the 26-year-old Suchir Balaji found dead in San Francisco in November 2024 ([BBC, 2024](#)). Before his untimely death, Balaji provided an explanation of OpenAI’s copyright issues with “specific analysis for ChatGPT’s use of its training data, but the same basic template will also apply for many other generative AI products”. His detailed missive can be read here: suchir.net/fair_use.html

Copyright infringement lawsuits are already underway against Microsoft, Intel, Nvidia, OpenAI, and others. The accused big tech companies claim justification of training their AI models on human creativity under “fair use” ([Sustainable Tech Partner, 2024](#)). Various copyright infringement cases include:

March 2025: Authors Guild “[Legal action ... underway against Meta, OpenAI, Microsoft, Anthropic, and other AI companies for using pirated books.](#)” “Meta and other AI companies knew exactly what they were doing but they did it anyway. ... they needed books for their quality writing, style, expression, and long-form narration and would rather steal them than ask and pay for them as they do for all of the other necessary components of their AI, such as electricity and programming” ([Authors Guild, 2025](#)).

If you have a book and/or publication and are wondering if it is included in Meta’s AI training data, try the tool created by **The Atlantic** here: [Search LibGen, the Pirated-Books Database That Meta Used to Train AI - The Atlantic](#)

“November 2024 - Canadian Media Lawsuit vs. OpenAI: Multiple [Canadian media companies have filed suit against OpenAI](#), alleging that "OpenAI regularly breaches copyright and online terms of use by scraping large swaths of content from Canadian media to help develop its products, such as ChatGPT. OpenAI is capitalizing and profiting from the use of this content, without getting permission

or compensating content owners." The plaintiffs include Torstar, Postmedia, The Globe and Mail, The Canadian Press and CBC/Radio-Canada."

“November 2024 - Potential Class Action Lawsuit: A Manchester law firm has started on-boarding clients for a [probable class action lawsuit against Microsoft and Google](#). [Barings Law](#) believes the cloud services giants are "unlawfully collecting and using peoples' personal data to train their artificial intelligence (AI) models".”

“November 2024 - New York Times Lawsuit Update vs. OpenAI: The New York Times says it spent 150 hours sifting through OpenAI's training data looking for potential evidence—only for [OpenAI to delete all of its work”](#).

The UK government's public consultation on copyright concluded at the latter end of February 2025. Over 11,000 responses were received, including missives from world renowned musicians including Kate Bush, Sir Elton John and Sir Paul McCartney. As part of the UK creative industry's 'Make it Fair' campaign ([FT, 2025](#)) a silent protest album was released to counter the UK government's proposal to change “copyright law to allow artificial intelligence companies to build their products using other people's copyrighted work - music, artworks, text, and more - without a licence” ([Is this What You Want, 2025](#)).

As well as copyright infringement, another threat from GenAI is the very real risk of job losses. The general public need to appreciate the very real risk of 'people replacement' promoted by companies developing AI employees and virtual agents (*Artisans*). If your work becomes too dependent on GenAI tools, unless you are showing evidence of actual productivity, and a real return on investment to your employer, you could be replaced with an AI.

Companies such as 'Artisan AI' promote ideas around their **agents not requiring work-life balance** (see Figure 1 overleaf taken from X/Twitter: [Eric Bourdages on X: "Hey look, artists were right, tech bros really are just petty & jealous of our existence. https://t.co/4Yy9EZVQIF" / X](#)).

ArtisanAI's virtual sales assistant, Ava, will, according to the company, automate the sales role, find “quality leads”, mine data, and craft personalised messages. More on her functionality here: [Hire Ava, the AI SDR | the Best AI Sales Agent](#) .

The idea of efficiency through virtual customer service agents is not new. In 2005 the company behind Ikea's 24/7 online digital customer agent, Anna, reported that Ikea's ROI on Anna was 200%, call-centre costs were down 20% and sales from its online catalogue increased by 10% (figures given to Huma Shah in 2005 for her presentation at the University of Surrey's colloquium on conversational systems in November 2005).

This trend at virtualising jobs is likely to continue at a rapid pace with GenAI tools.

[HBR](#) (2024) “analyzed 1,388,711 job posts from a leading global online freelancing platform from July 2021 to July 2023” and reported: “significant short-term job replacement after these tools were introduced, and that jobs prone to automation, like writing and coding, were the most affected by ChatGPT.”

Another aspect of virtualising the workplace could be the **lack of inclusivity and diversity in the future job market**. If fewer women use AI tools, perhaps due to limited digital skills, or if migrants are excluded from access-to-opportunities to try LLMs and GenAI tools, the future labour market could see overwhelming environments of men and AI agents, which could reduce the emergence of innovative ideas bursting from multiple views. [Forbes](#) (2023) querying AI on **why men were more likely to use GenAI tools such as ChatGPT** reported: “historically higher representation of men in the tech sector, which is likely to be the source of most early adopters.”.

Forbes also “asked on Twitter/X why the disparity might exist, one person cited the fact that historically AI tools like Alexa, Siri and Cortana have often had female names, playing into **cultural stereotypes about women helping men.**” (2023).

Figure 1: from X/Twitter showing ArtisanAI posters in San Francisco

Step 4: Variety of Generative AI tools with different functionalities

There are many tools, and more are emerging under the 'Generative AI' or GenAI headings. Search, research and summarisers include:

- AI Overview in Google search
- ChatGPT and its successors
- Copilot & Copilot for Researcher
- Claude
- DeepSeek
- Gemini (previously BARD founded on LaMDA)
- Google Notebook LM
- GROK
- Llama
- Perplexity AI

According to copilot (in December 2024), there are different categories of GenAI with various functionalities including:

1. **Content Creation:**
 - **ChatGPT:** Generates human-like text for chatbots, content writing, and more.
 - **Jasper:** Assists with marketing copy, blog posts, and social media content.
2. **Design and Visual Arts:**
 - **DALL-E:** Creates images from textual descriptions.
 - **Midjourney:** Generates artistic visuals and designs.
3. **Coding and Development:**
 - **GitHub Copilot:** Helps developers by suggesting code snippets and completing code.
 - **AlphaCode:** Assists in solving complex coding problems.
4. **Music and Audio:**
 - **AIVA:** Composes music for various genres and purposes.
 - **Amper Music:** Generates music tracks based on user inputs.
5. **Gaming and Entertainment:**
 - **DeepArt:** Transforms photos into artworks using styles of famous artists.
 - **RunwayML:** Provides tools for creating and editing videos with AI.
6. **Productivity and Business Tools:**
 - **Scribe:** Summarizes articles, crafts reports, and assists with academic writing.

- **Copy.ai:** Generates marketing copy, emails, and other business content.

Links to further information provided by copilot for the above:

[1] [20 Examples of Generative AI Applications Across Industries](#)

[2] [Top Generative AI Tools and Applications - Turing](#)

[3] [Top 35+ Generative AI Tools by Popularity & Category - AIMultiple](#)

The variety of AI tools is expanding; their capabilities will increase, and performances improve. Staying on top of this wave will be challenging. Nonetheless it will be necessary, because the labour market will demand AI skills in future jobs. The World Economic Forum's 'Future of Jobs Report' on the global labour market to 2030 forecasts ([WEF, 2025](#)):

“Advancements in technologies, particularly AI and information processing (86%); robotics and automation (58%); and energy generation, storage and distribution (41%), ... expected to be transformative. These trends are expected to have a divergent effect on jobs, driving both the **fastest-growing and fastest-declining roles**, and fueling **demand for technology-related skills, including AI** and big data, networks and cybersecurity and technological literacy, which are anticipated to be the top three fastest growing skills.”

Step 5: AI & the Digital Divide – Engaging the general public

Sufficient training for all stakeholders, inside and outside education (administrators, staff, students, technical staff, the general public, and SMEs, particularly small businesses), is required to complement current skills, update teaching, improve learning implementing a co-learning approach. This could contribute to safeguarding authentic creation of up-to-date and accurate content, alongside pedagogical and out-reach material from universities. Fostering critical thinking will be crucial with increasing dependence on LLMs and GenAI tools. Training to **test assumptions**, ensuring we avoid *believing in* and perpetuating misinformation and false data, will need to be sustained through evolving course curricula and regular roundtables with all stakeholders to illuminate confusion that exists, for example, around real questions such as 'What is the difference between machine learning and artificial intelligence?'. On student's work: Where an expected piece of student's assignment requires the use of an LLM or Gen AI tool, sufficient training should be provided to the students by GenAI-trained staff on how to use the tool for deeper understanding, not to replace learning (QAA, 2024). For example, Google's Notebook LLM could be used to understand how to conduct a literature review. This could help 'to go beyond', for example, describing 'what happened', such as in the case of algorithms used in recruitment, to critique the way in which something happened and how it could have been done differently to mitigate risk, prevent harm, benefit society:

“... algorithmic bias results in discriminatory hiring practices based on gender, race, color, and personality traits. ... indicates that algorithmic bias stems from limited raw data sets and biased algorithm designers.” (Zhisheng Cheng, 2023: [Ethics and discrimination in artificial intelligence-enabled recruitment practices | Humanities and Social Sciences Communications](#)).

Concluding

There is no ‘one artificial intellect’ yet. “Artificial Intelligence, AI for short, is an umbrella term for a set of loosely related technologies. ChatGPT has little in common with ... software that banks use to evaluate loan applicants” (page 1 in ***AI Snake Oil: What Artificial Intelligence Can Do, What it Can’t and How to Tell the Difference***, published by Princeton Press, 2024; authors: A. Narayanan and S. Kapoor).

What is important to stress is, it is beneficial to equip ourselves with different technologies to enhance our capabilities, including using digital, AI-driven ones. But there is a very real risk of ceding our learning to the current bucket of GenAI tools which can have deleterious affects on our ability to think and our capability to express our thinking coherently. Shallow understanding could lead to errors and damaging consequences. Use of current GenAI tools is advised with caution and responsibility, but necessary to meet demands of a changing labour market. We don’t want to lose jobs to Artisans!

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